

SQLITE FOR DATABASE PRESERVATION

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Abstract – SQLite is a compelling choice for database preservation. What’s missing in order to make it really viable? This poster explores the advantages of SQLite, identifies standards and tooling needed to make it excel in a digital preservation context, and showcases a proof-of-concept software application that demonstrates this.

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The advantages of SQLite for this purpose are several:

- it is widely used (it is the most used database in the world)
- it is portable, single file and serverless
- open source
- public domain
- has a fully specified, public file format
- SQLite software is extensively tested.

SQLite is also a very accessible format. Although you can’t open and read the database in a text editor, you probably wouldn’t want to do that for a large and complex database anyway. Instead, you can use the SQLite command line tool to view the database schema, perform queries, and export results. Or you could use any of several open source programs that work with SQLite, including Datasette, a tool for exploring and publishing data [5].

SQLite is well suited for database preservation but what is missing in order to make it a preferred choice for digital preservation practitioners?

This poster assesses the standards and tooling required for SQLite to be more useful in a digital preservation context. The poster also showcases a proof-of-concept application for migrating databases to SQLite with embedded digital preservation metadata.

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

It is often desirable, when migrating database-backed systems to digital archives, to perform some kind of database migration. This may be because the receiving archive doesn’t have the technical capacity to maintain ongoing access to the system in its original form, or because the donor is only transferring a subset of the data, or for the purpose of creating a secondary version of the database for redundancy or access.

In such a scenario, there are several choices to consider for the target format for the migration, including structured text-based formats like JSON, XML or CSV. SIARD is a common choice in the digital preservation community [1]. Another option, recommended by the Library of Congress as a format for dataset preservation [2], and one of the options in the DPC’s Preserving Databases guidance note [3], is SQLite [4].

REFERENCES

- [1] SIARD (Software Independent Archiving of Relational Databases). <https://dilcis.eu/content-types/siard>
- [2] Recommended Formats Statement. Library of Congress. <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/resources/rfs/data.html>
- [3] Preserving Databases. Digital Preservation Coalition. July 2021. <https://www.dpconline.org/docs/technology-watch-reports/2470-preserving-databases/file>
- [4] SQLite. <https://sqlite.org/>
- [5] Datasette. <https://datasette.io/>

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